

APPLYING TAYLORISM IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION: EFFECTS ON EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN ABIA STATE GOVERNMENT

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Abstract:

This study examined Taylor's ideals and employees' performance in Abia state civil service. As we know Performance, in all its guises, occurs across all organizations whether formally through an official organizational process or informally through personal relationship. Given its inherent importance, this study conducted a review of performance using the ideals and tenets of Taylor in Abia State civil service. The study recommended among others cooperation between management and employees in order to ensure all aspect of the job is executed in conformity with the principle of science (policy) being developed for greater performance. The suggested a series of knowledge gaps which, if filled, will help both management scholars and practitioners better understand how employee performance can be effectively managed using Taylor's principles.

Keywords: Taylor Ideals; Employees Performance; Civil Service

Introduction:

The world round development, especially economic development and prosperity of nations depends on the contribution of firms/organizations operating at various levels and sectors of the economy. Though, both profit and non-profit organizations, manufacturing and service as well as private and public sectors all contribute to economic development of nations, the public sector acts as the custodian of laws and regulations, oversees the economic development of nations, provides employment, provide infrastructures (roads, railways, airports and hospitals etc.)

required to support economic growth, encourages reasonable developments, as government services are provided at remote areas of society and so on. In Nigeria, the public sector is the engine that propels the nations' economic development and the point at which accelerated growth in all areas of the economy is hinged. This sector is made up of public service and public enterprise. The public service is intended to serve the interest of all members in a given society these include healthcare, courts, electricity, education, social services, water supply networks, transportation infrastructure, telecommunication, waste management, emergency services etc(Agwu, 2013). These services are controlled and managed by an arm of the executive often referred to as civil service commission.

The civil service as an arm of the executive is responsible for implementing and enforcing the policies and programmes of government. As opined by (Ipinlaiye, 2001), civil service refers to the group of individuals employed by federal, state and local governments in a civil capacity and in non-partisan basis for rendering, and trustworthily giving effect to the decisions and implementations of governments' programmes. Though, the establishment of the civil service was traceable to antiquity and not a formation of modern time, it emerged as a foundation of the execute arm of government with the rise of the modern state as well as the parliamentary system

of government. The civil service provides and oversees access to public goods and services, manages public expenditure and revenues as well as maintains the sustainability of public finances and also ensures overall institutional development. Though not adequate, a necessity for good governance often hinges on skilled, inspired and efficient civil service with professional tenet (Rao, 2013). In Nigeria, governments at various levels (mainly the state and federal) have sought for ways of improving the civil service through restructuring and introduction of various reforms.

Despite the various reforms and restructuring, events have shown that the commission still remains stagnant and unproductive. However, issues like poor attitude to work, strikes/picketing, resistance to change, political instability as well as interference, bureaucratic bottle-neck, duplication of offices and positions, inadequate qualified workforce, ineffective organization, lack of initiative, bribery and corruption, tribalism and nepotism have been seen to have bedeviled the commission. These issues span across the various states of the federation of which Abia State civil service is part of. These issues have violated the core values (integrity, impartiality, professionalism, commitment to the rule of law and objectivity) of the commission as outlined in the civil service code. Though, productivity in the private sector cannot be equated with what is obtainable in the public sector, poor work ethics as well as low-capacity building/utilization have militated against improved productivity in the Nigerian civil service (Ajakaiye, 2000). These issues have had devastating effect on the economy of the state, as they result in infrastructural decay, inefficiency in the various commissions, agencies and parastatals, lack of trust and despair on the government by the citizens amongst others.

Though, several studies (Ajakaiye, 2000; Adebayo, 2014; Okeke, Nwele, Acilike, 2017) have been conducted on productivity in the civil service in Nigeria, none exist to ascertain the ideals Federick Taylor and workforce productivity in Abia State civil service. Against this background, the study examines the ideals and tenets of Taylor as the foundation of workforce productivity in Abia State Civil Service Commission. Therefore, the study seeks to examine the ideals and tenets of Taylorism as the foundation of workforce productivity in Abia State civil service. Specifically, the study examines the nature and workforce productivity of civil service in Abia State as well as the Principles of Taylorism on workforce performance in Abia state's civil service.

Conceptual Clarifications

Taylor's Ideals

In Taylor's view, the task of management was to determine the best way for the worker to do the job, to provide proper tools, training, and incentives for good performance. The tenets of scientific management opined that science should be developed for each element of work which replaces the old rule-of-thumb method of management. In other words, task assigned to employees must be observed, analyze in relation to each element as well as time taken to accomplish the job.

Employees Performance

This denotes how well workers execute their job, duties and responsibilities. It is a measure of how an employee achieves their duties, role and behaves within the workplace. Employees' performance is an important aspect of the business because it can make or mar the organization. Employees' performance includes the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of an employee's output. An employee's performance is also indicative of how valuable they are to the organization. Employees are deemed an investment to the organization, so their return on investment is essentially calculated by their performance.

Civil Service: The civil service is a collective term for a sector of government composed mainly of career civil servants hired rather than appointed or elected, whose institutional tenure typically survives transitions of political

leadership. A civil servant, also known as a public servant, is a person employed in the public sector by a government department or agency for public sector undertakings.

Theoretical Foundation

The study is anchored on Frederick Winslow Taylor's scientific management theory propounded in 1911. Taylor's scientific management in his publication "principle of scientific management", although, the term 'scientific management' was coined by Louis Brandeis in 1910 during the famous Eastern Rate Case, in the search for achieving greater efficiency (Sidorick, 2015). Taylor is of the belief that making people work is not as efficient as optimizing the way the work was done. The objectives of scientific management approach are to determine the basic principle of motion involved in executing physical task and then ascertain the 'one best way' of accomplishing any task. Taylor viewed employee to be habitually lazy and thus contributes to the problems of inefficiency through deliberate and organize restriction of output also known as 'systematic soldiering'.

According to Taylor, social prosperity lies on the combine efforts of management and employees in the application of scientific methods (Sapru.R.K., 2013). Scientific management lies on four major principles which were a blend of mechanical, conceptual and philosophical ideas. These principles are: develop a science for every aspect of individual's work which replaces guesswork and not rule of the thumb.

Scientifically select, train as well as develop employees to ensure that they possess the necessary physical and mental qualities required to perform tasks.

Wholeheartedly cooperate with employees in order to ensure that all aspect of the job is executed in conformity with the principle of science being developed and not discord.

An equal division of work and responsibility between management and workers. Management should assume responsibility for which they are better suited than the workmen, whereas, previously all the responsibilities and jobs were left in the hands of workmen.

The central point of the theory is ensuring efficiency at the workplace, as the traditional management practices emphasis is on initiative as well as incentive management, thus placing much responsibility on workers. However, job design that lays too much emphasis on initiative and incentives, often this makes management neglect its responsibility of providing instruction and guidance to workers on the best way of accomplishing tasks which eventually leads to inefficiencies at the workplace. Thus, successful performance of organizations requires the combine efforts of management and workers in applying scientific management. In addition, as opined by Taylor, one of the causes of inefficiency at the workplace is the ignorance as to the proper time necessary to accomplish a given task. This led to the investigation of time and motion studies.

Ostensibly, Taylor is known as the father of scientific management, Henry Gantt, Frank and Lilian Gilbreth, Harrington Emerson all made significant contribution to the development of scientific management theory. Notably, Frank and Lilian Gilbreth contributed towards the use of motion pictures in which employees are filmed while performing work, then later replay the film to analyze workers 'motions and ascertain which aspect of the job (movement) is irrelevant that needs be jettison. Gantt was noted for developing a chart which provides a graphic schedule for the planning and controlling of work as well as recording progress towards stages of projects while Harrington was noted for his contribution on efficiency (Baridam, 2002). As opined by (Taylor, as cited in Sapru, 2013), the theory is categorized into three main components which include:

Time-and-motion study, wage-incentive system and functional organization. Time and motion studies put forward standards for performances of specific task, accounting the capacity, speed and durability of the worker. This component of scientific management theory stresses on several steps that must be applied in getting the best out of individual worker(s). These steps involve (a) Provision of the best tools to workers, (b). Division of work into

elementary units, (c). Discarding irrelevant movement, (d). the use of stopwatch for analysis, (e). Grouping basic movement of task into proper sequence in order to maximize efficiency, (f). Allowing workers some time to rest in order to recover from tiredness, (g). allowing new employee time to learn the job.

Another component of the scientific management theory is wage-incentive system. In this system, employees are given a specific task as well as detailed instructions and specific time required to carry-out such task. If employees accomplish the task at the allotted time, extraordinary wages are paid to them contrarily if they exceed the time allotted to them, they are paid ordinary wage for work done (Taylor, 1911 as cited in Sapru, 2013). This approach encourages success through payment of higher wages while penalizing failure through financial loss.

Lastly, functional organization on the notion of functional foremanship emphasizes the need for better supervision of workers. The idea lies on the decentralization of authority from general management and a centralization of authority from the foreman. Taylor opined that functional organization be based on a set of technical expertise in positions of power in the organization. His idea on functional foremanship states that workers be responsible to different technical experts in the position of power at the workplace. However, power should rest on the planning department rather than on the top level of the organization and knowledge should be seen as the exercise of authority instead of mere position. Moreover, while managers at strategic apex are to limit themselves only on challenges beyond the control of planning departments, experts from the planning department should be free from bureaucratic tendencies inherent in top hierarchy. However, the theory emphasizes the effective use of organizational resources while reducing wastage in effort, materials, times as well as skills. Hence effective use and implementation of scientific management principles will likely increase productivity in the Abia State civil service.

Overview of Civil Service in Abia State and Nigeria.

Civil service in Nigeria is coordinated by the civil service commission, a government agency that is constituted by legislature to regulate the employment and working conditions of civil servants, oversee hiring and promotions, and promote the values of the public service in Nigeria. Its role is analogous to that of the human resources department in organizations. Civil service commissions are often independent from elected politicians. The commission reviews government statutory powers to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in meeting public sector management objectives. It also acts as the human relations department, or central personnel authority, for the citizens' interactions with the government.

The origin of the public service commission in many jurisdictions in Nigeria, was the White Paper Colonial 197 issued in 1950, which set out measures which were proposed to improve the quality and efficiency of the colonial Service of the British administration. The setting up of public service commission was proposed in its paragraph 21(xi) which mentioned that:

Public Service Commission should be established in the Colonies. Subject to the general overriding powers of the Secretary of State, the selection and appointment of candidates in the colonies to posts in the local service will lie with the Governor of the Colony. It is desirable that the Governor should be advised in these matters by a Public Service Commission appointed by him and so composed as to command the confidence of the Service and the public; and that: {such Commissions should be established in the Colonies to advise the Governor on the selection and appointment of candidates to posts in the local service, and should be so composed as to command the confidence of the Service and the public} Wikipedia.

The current population of Abia State is estimated to be 5 million+ within the seventeen local government areas of the State, the state civil service originates from the Nigerian civil service which was established by the British during the colonial era. Though, it existed since the colonial era, the creation of Abia" is an acronym formed from

the initial letters of four groups of people, namely: Aba, Bende, Isuikwuato and Afikpo. These constituted the major groups in the state at its creation. At the country's independence in 1960, Abia was part of the then Eastern Region. From 27th May, 1967, it became a part of the East Central State, created by the then Head of the Federal Military Government, General Yakubu Gowon. On 3rd February, 1976, East Central State was split into two states (Anambra and Imo) by the Federal Military Government headed by General Murtala Mohammed. On 27th August, 1991, the Federal Military Government under General Ibrahim Babangida carved out Abia State from Imo State, bringing to thirty the number of states in Nigeria. Furthermore, in October, 1996, the Federal Military Government under General Sani Abacha created six more states bringing to thirty-six the number of states in the federation. This brought various administrative functions responsible for running the day-to-day affairs of the state to the newly created state.

The Abia state civil service is a body of professional civil servants that is responsible for executing the policies of the Abia state government regarding infrastructural development as well as social service delivery (Abia State, 2011). More so, the service/its agencies regulate the public and private sectors of the economy of the state, monitor policy performance as well as serves the various organs of the state government. The service is governed by the 'head of Service', a member of the executive council who is seen as the most senior administrative official within the civil service of Abia state. The Abia state civil service is composed of several ministries and parastatals wherein civil servant performs their tasks based on qualifications and seniority. The ministries are controlled by Permanent secretaries who often give administrative reports to the commissioners. The permanent secretary provides continuity and is responsible for operations while the commissioner is in charge of the policies.

The ministries among others include: Agriculture, Budget and economic planning, chieftaincy and community affairs, commerce and industries, culture and tourism, education, energy and natural resources, employment generation and empowerment, environment, finance, health, sports, transportation, youth development and so on (Government of Abia State, 2011). The Abia state civil service, given the necessary support like other civil services in Nigeria, expects her civil servants to share and supports the core values of the service – integrity, meritocracy, discipline, professionalism, patriotism impartiality as well as secrecy of government information.

The Nature and Workforce Productivity of Abia State's Civil Service.

Abia state civil service like other civil service until the 1988 civil service reforms tailored towards structural reorganization, professionalization and the enforcement of public accountability was organized in conformity with the British pattern of administration which was apolitical. That is, civil servants were expected to serve the government of the day in a non-party affiliated manner. Norms of impersonality and hierarchical authority were well established. However, the rapid expansion of the public sector as well as the complexity surrounding societal needs necessitated various reforms in the civil service. The Nigerian civil service have witnessed several reforms Harragin Commission in 1946, which divided the service into Junior and Senior services; Gorsuch Commission of 1954, which restructured the service into five (5) sections, which are: the subclerical, clerical, sub-professional/technical, administrative/professional, and super-scale; the Mbanefo Commission of 1959 which concerned mainly with the issue of salaries; Hewn Commission 1959 which integrated the existing departments under Directors into ministries to be headed by Permanent Secretaries, with a view to building a public service whose work is development, result- and people-oriented service. Though, these reforms were in existence before the birth of Abia State, among which, is the establishment of Udoji Commission in 1970 by Yakubu Gowon to harmonize the structure and organization of the public service in Nigeria.

However, the commission in 1974, recommends a result focus and unified structure (that is, recruitment/appointment, promotion, remuneration, retirement, discipline and dismissal governed by the same

conditions all over the country PSRC, 1974) for public service all over the entire states of the country for which Abia State is inclusive. In addition, reforms in Abia State civil service have given considerable amount of autonomy to allow ministries and departments exercise authority on matters concerning recruiting, training and development, downsizing, promotion, performance and appraisal management. Pay scales are made based on hierarchical grades often differentiating employees and positions relatively on skills, experience as well as knowledge for the job. More so, workplace diversity in forms of sex, race, age, ethnicity, physical ability, education and so on, has implication for the civil service in Abia state. Reports indicates that the number of women occupying senior civil service position have increased remarkably in Abia state civil service. The essence of these reforms is to make the civil service more efficient and result oriented in its operations.

Despite these reforms, the Abia State civil service is still characterized with pay roll fraud and large number of redundant post as well as undue influence from political office holders. As opined by (Adegbami, A & Uche, C. I.N , 2016) inadequate qualified manpower and non-committed as well as un-devoted personnel permeate all ministries as well as parastatals of the state civil service. Civil servants in Abia state exhibits poor attitude to work which is often displayed through tardiness, departure from the workplace before closure time, covert and overt resistance to change, absence to work, incessant complains on health issues, dereliction of official duties in attending to sales of personal wares from one office to the other and so on. Also, there is the issue of 'Ghost workers' permeating all ministries and parastatal which often results to over-bloated workforce figure. Though, there is over-bloated figure of workforce in Abia state's civil service, a new photographic finger-print electronic identity system introduced in 2005 which enabled the government, collect accurate data on the workforce of the state's civil servants thereby controlling the issues of ghost workers, often characterizing the state's civil service. The implication of the issues above is low productivity and erosion of integrity, professional value / ethics. Workforce productivity has been acknowledged as one of the most challenging issues facing organizations, in the field of management, (Hanaysha, 2016). Productivity is viewed to be the capability in realizing set objectives within a given period of time at an acceptable standard as well as a particular cost (Ahmed & Mehmood, 2012). However, several authors have given various definitions to explicate employee productivity. For instance, employees' productivity is seen as the time used in accomplishing a job by an employee for the purpose of achieving expected result based on the job description (Ferreira and Du Plessis 2009). Similarly, Mathis & Jackson (2000) see employee productivity as the quantity as well as the quality of job accomplished by an employee, considering the cost of resource utilized in achieving such job. Buttressing, the success or failure of firms, be it in the private or public sector can be likely attributive to the productivity of its employees.

Thus, as opined by (Olori, W.O. & Dan-Jumbo, C.T., 2017), organization, be it private or public, makes every effort in maintaining workforce capable of exhibiting greater positive job outcomes such as commitment, satisfaction, loyalty as well as identification while eliminating lower negative work outcomes such as intention to leave, incivility and dishonesty. Howbeit, productivity of employees in the Abia State civil service is often abysmally low. Notably, the factors contributing to this, is poor employee job outcomes shown in the level of indiscipline which manifests itself in the high rate of personnel tardiness, nonchalant attitude of workers towards work/clients, impudence, inefficiency, poor level of transparency, unaccountability, dismal level of productivity, indolence and above all corruption (Agwu M.O., Garba, A. & Jirgi, I.M, 2015); Garba & Jirgi, 2014). Resuscitating the low level as well as the counter-productivity characterizing the Abia state civil services, this implies developing a workforce that are emotionally attached as well as satisfied, and are willing to exert higher level of efforts in attaining organization objectives. This necessitates reviewing and applying the ideals and tenets of scientific management, often referred to as 'Taylorism'.

Principles of Taylorism on Employees Productivity in Abia State Civil Service.

Fredrick Winslow Taylor advocated for the scientific management based on certain principles seen as the solution to the problem of inefficiency characterizing the workplace. Though, several organizational and management theories have been developed to enhance workplace productivity both in the public and private sector, notably, scientific management is seen as one of the most important approaches to the efficient utilization of organizations' human resource and anchors on the application of 'one best' approach to management. However, emphasis is on efficiency, as opined by Taylor implies that management has the responsibility of making itself efficient before expecting efficiency from the workers. This could be achieved when management discovers the proper method applicable to employees in discharging their task.

This contrary expectation by parties in the achievement of organizational goals, places society on growth and developmental trajectory, thus, corroborating the views of Taylor as cited in Sapru (2013) which states that prosperity of society is achieved through the combine efforts of management and labour in applying scientific approach. Succinctly, one of the most striking features as observed by Taylor contributing to inefficiency is referred to as 'systematic soldiering'. To Taylor this arises, when people work in groups and is seen as an attempt of employees to hide themselves. This is seen as an organized or purposeful restriction of output by workers (Sapru, 2013).

This anomaly is what characterizes the public sector in Abia state, most notably the civil service.

Civil servants deliberately restrict output through exhibiting nonchalant attitude towards task.

Employees in the civil service see government work as job not for anybody (that is, since it belongs to the government, it is nobody's business). This brings to mind the popular belief held by public sector workers that 'whether the business prospers or not, labourers must be fully remunerated of their wages'. As opined by (Adeoti, 2011), nonchalant attitude can be learnt from experience or imitated from coworkers at the workplace, it is like a viral infection; it has the power to place organization in a disadvantaged position. Most times civil servants hide under the platforms of labour union to systematically restrict outputs. This is achieved through incessant demands for wage increase, better working condition, security of job, with little or no effort in increasing productivity contrarily to what is obtainable in the private sector.

However, the tenets of the scientific management rest on solving the problems of inefficiency characterizing the workplace. Efficiency is the measure of how effective an employee is able to accomplish a task within a specified period in relation to the approach chosen which suits that condition (Olugbemi, 1988). Unarguably, efficiency is unattainable in a work environment where there is high level of indiscipline, corruption, bureaucratic tendency and so on, characterizing the civil service in Abia state as well as Nigeria at large. Although, increased efficiency is unachievable in the prevailing work condition of the State civil service, application of strategy and philosophy that is driven by a relevant theory becomes the tool at which desire goals can be attained. Therefore, the assumption is the application of Taylor's scientific principles as the root through which increase efficiency can be achieved in the civil service.

These principles are discussed below in relation to the problems bedeviling the civil service in Abia state, Nigeria. The tenets of scientific management opined that science should be developed for each element of work which replaces the old rule-of-thumb method of management. In other words, task assigned to employees must be observed, analyze in relation to each element as well as time taken to accomplish the job. Rather than making decision based on guesswork, management must rely on scientific approach. In the civil service, scientific method should be applied to determine standard time required to accomplish a task. Though, there is resumption time and departure time for work, do civil servant use the time allotted to them to accomplish given sets of tasks necessary

for the day's work? Heads of departments in the various ministry must ensure that each element of the task are careful analyzed in terms of standardize time required to execute them. Similarly, fair day's work for civil servant should be determined by management. In addition, standardize tools and as well as equipment should be adopted and standard working conditions maintained. Rather than relying on the rule of thumb method in decision making which has adverse effects on productivity in the civil service, standardize approach as mentioned earlier be applied in all facets of the task.

Since, most civil servants see the job as no man's business, they report to work knowing next to nothing as regards what to accomplish for the day and how to measure the days' work output but beliefs that 'whether the business prospers or not, labourers must be fully remunerated for their wages', standardization becomes the rudder in which this anomaly can be controlled and objective accomplished. In other words, decisions must depend on scientific examination (analysis) with cause-and-effect relations rather than reliance on human judgment. Standardization cannot be achieved in an organization wherein the wrong person or group of individuals employed to perform task, thus, the next principles of scientific management 'scientifically select, train and develop employee(s) in ensuring that they possess the quality required to perform the job.

In addition, Taylorism advocates scientific selection, training as well as development of employees to ensure that they possess the necessary physical and mental qualities required to perform tasks. Notably, the civil service is one of the public sectors in Nigeria that is highly known for promoting ethnic/tribal sentiment in relation to recruitment processes. Substantiating, Adebayo (1992) notes that one of the issues bedeviling the Nigerian civil service is the recruitment of mediocre or totally unsuitable candidates in place of those who are highly qualified. This can be attributed to undue political influence as well as nepotism which is seen as leadership failure. The 'federal character' or quota system of recruitment policy in a bid of promoting national integration negates the dictates of meritocracy. Impartiality and professionalism which are seen as aspects of the core values of the civil service is maintained when the procedure for selection of workers is scientifically designed. Similarly, the selected workers should be given adequate training from time to time to avoid wrong methods of task execution. As noted by Singh & Mohanty (2012), training is a central and powerful instrument for the effective achievement of organizational objectives, resulting in greater productivity.

Though, the civil service commission recommended in 1988 and 1999 that ten percent of the total annual staff remuneration be earmarked for staff training and development, these recommendations were never implemented thereby making it difficult for most workers to cope with the changing nature of the work settings as occasioned by technological advancement. When workers are scientifically trained and developed, they get acquainted with new technology and how to handle materials and machines economically, rates of industrial accident reduced, lesser need for supervision, higher sense of job satisfaction, reduced employee turnover and increased organizational productivity. All of these benefits are unachievable in an atmosphere of rancor and uncooperativeness.

Taylorism emphasizes cooperation between management and employees in order to ensure that all aspect of the job is executed in conformity with the principle of science being developed. Permanent secretaries and heads of departments in the ministries should ensure that close cooperation exist between them and workers. This requires change of mental attitudes between employees and management. This, Taylor referred to as mental revolution. In the spirit of close cooperation and harmony, there are fewer industrial disputes that culminate into strikes, lockouts, demonstrations and so on. Permanent secretaries and workers should cooperate to ensure that there is increased productivity and creation of the spirit of mutual trust and confidence.

To ensure efficiency at the workplace, scientific management advocates an equal division of work and responsibility between management and workers. That is, management should assume responsibility for which they are better suited than the workmen, whereas, previously all the responsibilities and jobs were left in the hands of workmen. Unarguably, the civil service in Nigeria and Abia state in particular, often absorbed workers who are incompetent for positions for which they were not specialize in. As observed by (Ezeani, E. O, & Nwankwo. B.C., 2002), it is no longer strange to even find a graduate of religion functioning as a human resource manager/officer especially among the civil servants in the Nigerian State and local government system. Thus, it is unbelievable to infer that civil servants in Nigeria are all employed and placed on the job based on their capability as well as expertise. Nepotism as well as 'political god fatherism' place individuals in positions that their skills and expertise does not fit. However, to achieve efficiency in the civil service, permanent secretaries in the ministries should be responsible for planning and organizing task while civil servants should ensure that they performed their duties based on the instructions of the head of service and departments.

Conclusion:

Scientific management paved the way for enhancement of organization in the private as well as the public sectors, though, its principles had existed for more than a century, and it is still useful and applicable in today's business management. Considering the level of inefficiency characterizing the public sector, it would be misleading for one to jettison Taylorism from understanding efficiency in the service of the public sector. Taylorism promotes a new culture and values in the management of organizations' resources, most notably the human resource element of organization. Though, Taylorism has been severely criticized for reducing human beings to the condition of mere machine, with its emphasis on research, planning, standardization as well as cooperation, it also encourages management in making decision based on the laws of the situations rather than reliance on individuals' guesswork. However, several reforms have been made to ensure that the civil service becomes efficient and productive but little or no changes have been reported. The opium that the use of principles of Taylorism in the operations of Abia State's civil service, becomes the solution to the problem of inefficiency often observed in the service and as well ensure workforce productivity.

Therefore, the study recommended among others cooperation between management and employees in order to ensure that all aspects of the job is executed in conformity with the principle of science that is scientific management (Taylorism) being developed for greater performance.

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